

Satellite monitoring of mountain pastures: statistical characterization of different habitats based on spectral properties

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Introduction: Mountain pastures host rich plant biodiversity organized in various distinct habitats. An accurate long-term monitoring, going beyond the sole ground survey, is of primary importance for nature conservation and forage production planning. Within the GrassSense project, we develop a novel analytical framework to identify and monitor plant communities in mountain pastures based on the joint statistical analysis of ground data and satellite imagery. The driving research questions are whether it is possible to distinguish mountain pasture communities using commonly available satellite imagery and which analytical workflow and satellite products are suitable to track spatial and temporal changes.

Materials and methods: After a preliminary exploratory analysis, we developed a workflow consisting of the following steps: 1) We consider as study zone the mid-to-high elevation mountain pastures surrounding the Swiss National Park in the Grisons canton, mapped over approx. 100 sq. km for pasture vegetation associations, including fertile pastures, wetlands, dry plant communities, and dwarf shrubs. 2) We couple the ground classification to the reflectance signal measured in satellite images of the public product Sentinel-2 (European Space Agency): in particular we compute the NDVI spectral index, which is a proxy for living vegetation and detects greening activity. 3) Moreover, we analyze the effect of mountain shadows on the measured reflectance. To do that, we compute the shadow cast by mountains at the time the acquisition and we create a mask to divide the pixels in the shadow from the ones in the sun. Then we analyze the statistical distribution of NDVI separately for the shaded and sunny pixels (*Figure 1*). 4) Finally, we analyze the annual seasonality by considering multiple monthly images and the interannual variability by dividing two ensembles of annual data, the ones from particularly dry years and from wet years.

Figure 1 NDVI annual curves for three pasture types, Grisons Canton (preliminary results based on Landsat TM), with fraction of shaded pixels.

Results: The results show that pasture habitats present different statistics in the reflectance data, linked to their phenological cycle. Also, the effect of mountain shadows is low in the summer months, while it is more accentuated in Autumn, when spectral bias due to light scattering is more prominent. Moreover, since NDVI is mapped in both time and space, it is possible to generate maps of early greening activity to monitor the pastures and detect differences in dry and humid years.

Conclusion: The workflow developed in this study suggests that remote sensing imagery of mid-to-high resolution constitutes a valid auxiliary tool to monitor the vegetation variability in mountain pastures, and to characterize, spatiotemporally and for different habitats, the changes in the phenological cycle due to different water availability conditions. Future studies will be devoted to refine this type of analysis with a link to plant physiology indicators, which are physically measurable on the field.

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